

WAYS OF PREPARING FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY ON THE BASIS OF DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses ways, methods and methods of preparing students for professional activity based on the development of critical thinking. Also, the main elements of preparation for professional activities based on the development of critical thinking in students in the educational process and non-auditory processes are presented.*

Keywords: *students, future specialist, critical thinking, critical thinking, professional activity, educational tasks, types of training, point of view, pedagogical education.*

Today, there are many ideas and scientific approaches regarding the improvement of educational content and teaching methods. The need to improve the forms and methods of teaching, which allow to achieve high quality and efficiency, and to harmonize philosophical, sociological, psychological, and pedagogical knowledge on personality formation is increasing [1].

Today, educational assignments and exercises serve to guide the subjects of the higher pedagogical education process to acquire new knowledge, to create initiative in them, to develop pedagogical thinking, to harmonize educational and scientific-pedagogical activities. The need to design aircraft types is increasing. The presented new knowledge should serve to expand the possibilities of the subjects of the higher pedagogical education process to independently manage and organize their pedagogical activities. Convenient use of these opportunities requires expanding the scope of knowledge provided to the subjects of the higher pedagogical education process. Creating knowledge about many special branches and fields of pedagogy in the subjects of higher pedagogical education process, expanding their scientific worldview and imagination serves to enrich the content of pedagogical activity in the future.

Globalization of the information space, openness and increasing mass communication are creating a diverse thinking environment in the society. It misleads a person who does not have a special social opinion and attitude. The task of modern pedagogy and psychology is to educate a person who thinks and works independently, actively participates in the life of society. It is known that up to now, a person's mental intellectual level is not determined by how much knowledge he has acquired, how much information and evidence he has retained in his memory, but by his ability to distinguish the necessary knowledge through critical thinking, by reviewing the information, is measured by the ability to come to an independent solution [2].

Leading experts offer the following models of educational spaces that help students develop critical thinking.

1. Development of intellectual (thinking) skills by teaching in the educational situation.

2. Transfer of skills and competencies to other situations (transition from training to extracurricular activities) by creating a learning environment in which the social practice of critical thinking exists in a distributed manner.

3. Mastering this practice by each student in pragmatic and effective communication and working in a group on specific subject content (transition from study to subject content) [3].

The main elements of preparation for professional activity based on the development of critical thinking in students in the educational process and non-auditory processes are determined by the following:

- the ability to confidently act on the presented material and assess the level of reliability of the recommended educational information;

- openness to non-standard methods of solving known and new problems, desire to learn new things;

- readiness for constructive dialogue with the teacher and partner, the ability to defend one's point of view and demonstrate flexibility;

- focus on self-diagnosis of the level of development of various skills and qualities based on the comparison of their results with the given standards;

- thinking about the direction of education in the context of preparation for future professional activity, their specific purpose, this or that sequence;

- reasonable expression and defense of one or another professional outlook position.

Determines the parameters that can be observed in the development of critical thinking in preparing students for professional activities. To be a critical thinker, a student should be able to:

1. Focus on the question.

2. Ask clarifying questions.

3. Evidence analysis.

4. Evaluation and interpretation of observations.

5. Making a conclusion about the reliability of the source.

6. Reflecting on one's thinking activity.

In order to develop critical thinking, it is essential that students ask questions that have the function of identifying implicit ideas and grounds on which to base a judgment or conclusion[4].

The first type of questions is what we are trying to learn and understand. They usually aim to clarify the topic of discussion, open up new aspects of it, and clarify ambiguity. Substantive questions - questions about the essence and nature of events, facts and their description, relationships, meaning.

The second type of questions is related to questions about the content, genesis and ontology of the content. These include questions about how the subject of research is built into the surrounding world, what and how it is connected, the forms of its existence and types of development.

The third type of questions are frame questions that allow you to gain general knowledge about the question, the method of acquiring knowledge, the approach, and the limits of knowledge application.

It is of particular importance to use the method of analyzing the behavior of students themselves and others in preparing them for professional activities based on the development of critical thinking in students. Because there will be differences and correlations between the evaluations of others and their own evaluations. In order to correctly perceive these differences by students, it is necessary to analyze the activities of oneself and others [5].

“Ideal” strategy. This is a strategy used to explain to students the dual nature of “critical thinking”. This strategy helps students develop critical thinking skills. They are helped to form the ability to identify problems related to cultural events, solve problems, find a suitable solution in the process of making a complex choice.

“Good – bad” strategy. This serves to form students' ability to distinguish and evaluate the positive and negative aspects of critical thinking. In the course of the training, students will be able to compare events, express their attitude towards them, and clearly imagine the way to choose in conflict situations.

“Association of concepts” strategy. With the help of this strategy, students are able to differentiate the concepts that represent the phenomena of different cultures, to understand their content, to understand their interrelationship, to compare them, to distinguish between important and unimportant aspects that negate and require each other. will help. With this strategy, students' ability to develop their cognitive abilities will be increased.

“Position - base - example – result” strategy. Within this strategy, students acquire the ability to express their thoughts about their chosen profession in a conscious and confident way. This strategy serves to form an objective point of view about the specific aspects of critical thinking in students, and is used at the stage of learning new information. It helps students to form a clear view of future professional activity. This strategy includes 4 important parts.

Position (point of view). Tell us about your chosen profession. You can use professional words to express yourself. Here professors and teachers require students to justify their opinion. Basis. Why do you think so in front of the students? the question is asked. They should start explaining their thoughts with the words “Because...”.

Examples. A student should use at least three arguments to explain his point of view. Through this, students try to justify their point of view. The words “For example ...”, “I can justify this with the following ... evidence” are used.

The result. In this final part, it is required to state the final conclusions that support the point of view. The phrases “Thus ...”, “In conclusion ...”, “Therefore ...”, “Based on the above”, “I came to the following conclusion ...” are used.

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